

ASSESSING LEARNERS' LANGUAGE COMPETENCES IN EXTROVERT AND INTROVERT CHARACTERISTICS

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Annotation. The role of language learning competencies is vital in a second language acquisition. Also, the individual characteristics of learner, such as extrovert or introvert, can require from educator to modify the ways of conducting lessons and lesson plan.

Key words: an extrovert, an introvert, speaking skill, writing ability. theory, observation, research.

Introduction

The case study depicted here effectiveness second language acquisition in introvert and extrovert personalities. The purpose of case study is to observe and analyze the participants learning process in various characters. The case study is based on 3 three stages; such as a questionnaire, a writing, a interview which are related to learning second language process.

The intention of case study is to prove of what extravert is well suited to communicate while introvert is good at writing and other fields. In this purpose we have tried to research some materials and information which are related to these personalities. In my small case-study we are going to justify diversity theories in practice whether an extravert is a good speaker while an introvert is a master in writing or vice versa.

The result of our case study will be convenient to our future teaching process. Because it might support to teach English Foreign Language (EFL) learners with different personalities in my working process. Also, the case-study will shown us how to communicate with different English Language Learners (ELL).

As experimental students we have chosen two ELLs at our university groups. They are both intelligent students who have been learning English for a long time so as to learn perfectly.

Literature review

There have been investigated several research works as well as doctoral dissertation in terms of effectiveness of Second Language Acquisition in extrovert and introvert personalities so far.

In terms of these personalities, Dawaele and Furham [1999] state that extroversion as well as introversion are a chunk of increase. Extroverts are social active learners who like speaking with somebody, therefore sometime they may be seen as enthusiastic and outgoing. Extroverts receive decisions quickly due to their risk-taker ability. However, introverts are those who are keen on spending time alone, furthermore they think a lot before acting and speaking. They prefer to work alone with somebody's assist, for this reason it is challenge for them to join a new and team as soon as possible.

Various researches are shown various results and ideas about learning foreign language with these characteristics. Eysenck [1952] was a scientist who studied first the interrelation between extroversion and learning second language in the globe. He claimed that extroversion was not effective individuality in foreign language acquisition due to neutron chemical sense in human mind, as a result he came to the point that being an introvert is a better way to learn second language.

The Second Language Acquisition (SLA) scientists were opponents of Eysenck's theory whether an extrovert person can learn a target language better than an introvert. For example, researcher Rossier [1976] has found that an extrovert learner has ability about language proficiency more rather than introvert. Furthermore, Tucker, Hamayan and Genesee [1976] have observed that immersion program was done better by outgoing personality members than quieter learners. Krashen [1985] claimed that the quantity of input is developed by extrovert learner.

There were some type of SLA theorists who claimed a totally different point. For example, Schneiber-Herzig [1984] said that there was no any definite relation between extroversion and SLA and he proved it his West German high school pupils who were learning English as a Second Language. Another researcher Nainman [1978] found out that theory with French students who were learning foreign language.

Participant profile

We have conducted this research work with our university students: the first learner (L1) is Bekhruz who studies at univeristy and he is now 20 years old boy. This language learner is Uzbek who was raised in a traditional family with national and traditional lifestyle. However, his lingual competence is multilingual which means he has capability in Russian which is second language than his mother tongue due to his studying place and zone of communication whether he shared his points as possible in Uzbek at home with

his family members. Plus, in terms of second language L1 is good at learning English, in other words he is in pre intermediate level learner , therefore he can understand and explain his personal point to listener with his best ability. Besides that, he enjoys speaking with other people in a target language, he is a flexible guy who can keep in touch easily to any atmosphere. In other words, his language awareness in both languages has made him adaptable to any learning environment. Therefore, his basic interpersonal communication skill is higher rather than other language learners..

The second learner's (L2) name is Sevinch who studies the same university in 3rd course who 19 years old girl. She is from Uzbek family who was brought up in a traditional family with national and spiritual values. She studies in Uzbek group, therefore her atmosphere is surrounded with monolingual speakers. When it comes to her second language, it is English. She has been learning this target language for 3 years simultaneously. This learner is also a talented scholar who is in pre intermediate level. She has achieved some results among her friends and classmates. The girl is studying with high GPA scores in order to continue her study process in the abroad. Sevinch is a shy person, therefore sometimes she can not explain her personal ideas in a classroom completely. Even she is a quiet person in real life, she is getting some success about learning acquisition.

L1 and L2 are our students at our university. We have been conducting English lessons to them for a long time. They are owners of different proficiencies in terms of language acquisition. Bekruz and Sevinch are presenting huge results rather than other learners, even though their outlook and characters are totally different. For example, L2 was accepted to Students union in this summer due to her high general scores. Moreover, she participated in essay contest which was at university was awarded with a silver medal at the end of the year. L1 also achieved some results, such as he is a Head Organizer of Youth Union at school because of his personal characters like easy-going, friendly, enthusiastic that sometimes support him to learn English as Foreign Language (EFL). In terms of cultural background of the participants, both of them were born in traditional Uzbek family whether spiritual and cultural features follow to national Uzbek mentality. We are totally convinced that these two learners are available to our case study with their personal characteristics in terms

of Second Language Acquisition (SLA). It is a fact that, both university students have enormous learning capabilities and cultural as well as language acquisition developments which are appropriate to our small scale case study.

Research design

Due to case study, we worked with our learners for some time in order to get to know their personalities perfectly whether he/she is extrovert or introvert and get intensive results. In order to observe their characters, we have divided our work to 3 parts: a. identifying their learning type b. writing module c. speaking module (interview)

Stage 1

In this section, we decided to gain data about the identification of the learner's characteristic type whether an extrovert student or an introvert one. So as to clarify this, we shared with some sheets to experimental students, the sheets which have been done before are Intro Extro Quiz. Regarding to quiz, there are 20 questions which should be chosen TRUE or FALSE answer based on learner's personal character and horizon. In terms of evaluation of quiz, after having answered to research questions researcher told to both learners to count their TRUE answers. Because according to quiz assignment, the more TRUE answers, the more introvert learner is. Also I explained what it is an informal quiz, it means there is no an exactly identity test and all questions are prepared based on temperaments of introversion. The author of quiz is Susan Cain, the name of quiz called *“The Power of Introverts in a World That Can't Stop Talking”*. Questions are mostly about activity circumstances (individual or group), conversations, expressing himself/herself, concentration, classroom situations, etc. Both experimental learners have done to answer in 5- 7 minutes because the level of questions are formulated in basic level.

Stage 2

In the following stage, we have conducted to write a letter which is captivating to learners to communicate with each other. In order to teach how to write a good letter, we have utilized some materials from the book which is called *“Academic writing”*. we have explained the types of letters such as formal and informal, afterwards the structure of letter like introduction, main body, conclusion. In the next step, in order to know what learners have understood or not, we have given a task to write a giving information letter to his/her friend

which is with informal way in 30 minutes. we handed out a sample written letter. Experimental students have done it in different times such as L1 has finished in 25 minutes while 20 minutes is enough for L2 to perform this task completely.

Stage 3

The next stage is speaking that is a fascinating part to learners. we have focused on what both students want to pass an IELTS exam in the near future, therefore questions are based on real test which are not complex to respond them. In this goal, we have used the book which is called “*IELTS speaking*” and chosen a topic is about bad habits which can interrupt them.

The question is:

Tell me about one or two bad habits you have. In your speech you should cover what the bad habits are, why you improved these, and how they affect your life

In order to carry out this task, they are given 3 minutes to prepare the speech and 2 minutes to talk about it. I guess speaking about their bad habits is not so challenge, because learners are ready to talk in 2 minutes. L2 could speak 1:29 seconds while L1 performed in 2 minutes which is time limit.

Data collection and findings

Based on Intro Extra Quiz which is first observation, we could find out that our learners characters are totally different each other, in other words L1 is an extravert learner while L2 is an introvert one.

In terms of L1, we took an experiment. Because it was clear to us from several contacted lessons of Business English group, L1 who is an extrovert participated to our lessons with his best abilities better rather than other members of the group. He likes to communicate more, also he has an ability to control the group which means he is an extremely social boy, plus he is keen on multitasking that might be tough to this level students. He tries to learn not only English at university, but also he is good at other subjects such as economics, critical thinking, etc. He enjoys to do an intellectual battle with other students, even one time he has won huge money on the topic which is incredible in this age. In general, in my opinion, he is the best sample to an extrovert ELL.

Regarding to L2 who is an introvert, L2 has a lot of TRUE replies to given IQ test. We think, the result is a rightful, as she is a quiet girl which likes spending time alone. Moreover, L2 thinks a lot before making some decisions and actions. She likes listening than speaking, therefore these features impact to her learning

acquisition process. I think it is an affect of home culture, because her mother said to me that girl are taught to listen more than speak in her house. Therefore, L2 has advantages and disadvantage in terms of second language, for instance L2 can learn any writing material faster than other students which is a few phenomenon among EFL learners. On the other hand, it is challenge to her to join a new team and group as soon as possible, for this reason she prefers to work alone without getting somebody's assist.

As a proof:

13. I I do my best work on my own.

Image 1st : The result of anonymous evaluation of introvert learner.

The second observation involved to write a letter, there were some diversities among learner. L2's letter is well written than L1's because she has organized well every detail, in other words every paragraphs has shown obviously with details especially introduction part is like a sample:

Image 2nd : A handwriting of introvert learner

It is known that, an introvert learner is an owner of wide horizon and outlook, so L2 tried to describe view with her best ability through awesome handwriting. As a teacher, we would evaluate this letter with high score. L1 who is an extrovert has attempted to point out his personal ideas. In general his writing style is ordinary, because he made some mistakes to perform the task. For instance, he was told to write an informal letter which is a giving information letter. But he wrote an formal one which task achievement has been lost. Furthermore, he had mistakes with word choice, grammar, spelling, punctuation:

Image 3rd : The letter of extrovert learner

It is generally accepted that, an extrovert learner is an excellent communicator but not a writer. So as a teacher we explained to this student how to write a good letter with details and sample.

Table 1. The Four Points Average of Writing Test of the Extrovert Student (L1)

Total	Task Achievement	Coherence and Cohesion	Lexical Resource	Grammar Range and Accuracy
Average	10	10	10	10
Mark	2	8	6	7

Table 2. The Four Points Average of Writing Test of the Introvert Student (L2)

Total	Task Achievement	Coherence and Cohesion	Lexical Resource	Grammar Range and Accuracy
Average	10	10	10	10
Mark	10	9	9	10

The **third observation** revealed speaking during max 2 minutes which is about one or two bad habits. The extravert learner (L1) has spoken in given time. We would say that, the extravert has done it better rather than an introvert. Firstly, he did not focus on time limit, also he could count several bad habits what he had. However, he had some drawbacks, such as grammar rules were totally broken, he had mistakes with pronunciation. In general, he could deliver his personal ideas to listener with almost clear points.

Table 3. The Four Points Average of Speaking Test of the Extrovert Student (L2)

Total	Fluency and coherence	Lexical resource	Grammatical range and accuracy	Pronunciation
Average	10	10	10	10
Mark	9	9	7	7

In terms of an introvert (L2) her voice is also acceptable but she had also some advantages and disadvantages in speaking process. For example, L2 could organized well with first, second transitions. Furthermore, she spoke less, so her speech was covered only a few information. She had hesitations while speaking, the main reason of this she was worry about to speak about her feelings in front of other people especially among her peers. I have known that the behavior of offspring is a prime focus which is home culture in her home.

Table 4. The Four Points Average of Speaking Test of the Introvert Student (L2)

Total	Fluency and coherence	Lexical resource	Grammatical range and accuracy	Pronunciation
Average	10	10	10	10
Mark	8	6	7	6

Conclusion

From my small-case study, it has been proved that extroversion as well as introversion are two perceptions that are broadly acknowledged in the globe. As Dewaele and Furnham [1999] stated tremendously extrovert and introvert person are various each other, put it differently ordinary extrovert is sociable, likes people to communicate. According to language methodology these people are always ready to answer orally instead of writing. When it comes to introvert learner, L1/L2 is a quiet learner who likes reading a book instead of keeping intimate friend, shortly telling L1/L2 can save feelings under close control.

It has been experimented that the theory which is about extrovert and learner language acquisition by Dewaele and Furnham is definitely true. Our extrovert L1 is socially active boy who is good at speaking rather than writing. Whenever he is at home, he can communicate well without any fences with his family and siblings, it means he does not hide his personal sensation inside. Based on SLA, this extrovert can learn language faster about speaking, plus he is not afraid of learn from his mistakes. Nevertheless, he might have drawbacks with reading and writing.

Regarding to the introvert learner, the theory is correct what our experimental learner likes writing to communicate. It might be true Eysenck [1952] theory whether an introvert is positively correlated with LLs, consequently an introvert is a better learner than extrovert. As it is shown in Table 2, an introvert learner (L2) has got high score in each assignment criteria. It seems to me that, an introvert is able to deliver her/his opinions through written form. L2 paid attention to speaking less rather than writing. I guess, it is a shortage of our traditional culture whether a girl should keep silence or not talk to much in some places. Therefore, her average score for each column is lower than L1's. So in the interview I advised her to be sociable among people and to communicate more with them. I hope my advice will be practical to her SLA. Because According to TESOL educational public policy, personality of learner definitely impact to his/her language learning process.

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